

SOCIAL AND SPIRITUAL FOUNDATIONS OF PATRIOTISM IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10480621>

Abstract. *The article reflects the importance of realizing peace and stability in the country as the highest good through social, spiritual and educational support for military personnel and, in connection with this, the importance of living and working with a sense of belonging for every citizen living in the country.*

Keywords: *activities of military personnel, spiritual and educational work, social and cultural life, patriotism.*

The defense capability of the new Republic of Uzbekistan and the high fighting power of the Armed Forces are directly related to the socio-economic, political, strategic and military-technical and scientific strength of the people of Uzbekistan and the upbringing of every citizen in the spirit of patriotism. That is why reforms in this regard are being implemented step by step in the new Uzbekistan. For example, according to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [1, p.1-2.], the Strategy of Actions on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 was determined. First of all, in the action strategy, attention is focused on fundamentally improving the activities of all levels of state administration bodies, ensuring their communication with the people, strengthening the mechanism of security, inter-ethnic harmony, religious tolerance and mutually beneficial constructive dialogue, and the mechanism of effective social cooperation. and this, in turn, is particularly important in educating the young generation in the spirit of selflessness and loyalty to the Motherland, these factors have been identified as one of the most important priorities of state policy in Uzbekistan. Also, on February 23, 2018, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approving the concept of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism" was adopted. Accordingly, it was decided to pay attention to the issue of comprehensive training of boys up to the age of military service and strengthening of the feeling of patriotism in their hearts. As a result, the teaching of military training subjects in the graduating classes of secondary education was left alone.

Decision No. PQ-3898 dated August 4, 2018 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On fundamental improvement of the system of raising the moral and educational level of the military personnel of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and this In accordance with the concept of increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in the Armed Forces system introduced on the basis of "The Motherland is sacred, it is an honorable duty to protect it!"

idea was put forward. Also, in the Armed Forces system, every Friday of the week is designated as the "Day of Moral Upliftment and Patriotism", and it is necessary to encourage the moral and spiritual training of military personnel. The goal is to faithfully protect the sovereignty, territorial integrity, and peace of our people. Large-scale reforms are being implemented in our country to strengthen peace and stability, ensure human rights, freedoms and interests, comprehensively develop our country, and raise its prestige in the international arena.

Therefore, education of the youth of our country in the spirit of military patriotism is one of the most important tasks according to the seven priority areas defined in the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the years 2022-2026. The bravery shown by our ancestors who lived in our great past, our great compatriots who defended our country from invaders in order to keep the peace of our people, fought valiantly against the enemy for the freedom of the Motherland - Shiroq, Tomaris, Spitamen, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Temur Malik, Najmuddin Kubro, Amir Temur. we are always proud to set an example for our military personnel. Currently, our Armed Forces have improved significantly in terms of organization and structure. The mobility of structures, combat capability, and physical and moral readiness of the military have increased. Military units and divisions were provided with modern weapons and combat equipment. The work being carried out to fill our national army with professional personnel, to further improve the training, knowledge and skills of military personnel [2, p. 37-38.].

The head of our state made it a task to constantly pay attention to the improvement of the moral and spiritual training of military personnel. Emphasizing that the scope of work on the organization of military-patriotic and spiritual-educational events aimed at increasing the sense of pride of the military personnel in their national and cultural heritage on the example of the great thinkers of the Uzbek people in the troops of the Ministry of Defense should not be reduced from the agenda, "Military "There is no military knowledge without science."

Issues of social protection of military personnel, adjustment of family conditions, provision of housing and accommodation are being implemented step by step. In order to increase the prestige of the military service in our country and further increase the combat readiness of our Armed Forces, special attention is paid to the issues of filling the troops with young and potential personnel, creating favorable conditions for military service, and ensuring the social protection of military personnel and their family members. According to the decision "On additional measures - activities related to the social support of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and their family members", the general admission quotas for the children of military personnel to the full-time bachelor's degree courses of higher educational institutions established on the basis of a state grant additional admission quotas are allocated on the basis of a state grant in the amount of five percent. Also, the necessary conditions for ensuring the health of military personnel and their family members have been created. Families in need of housing are provided with housing in the prescribed manner.

Based on our national mentality, even if there is only one son in the family and the rest are girls, these young men are given the privilege of serving in the area where their parents live, have a positive recommendation, and are given a rank higher than officers who have completed at least two years of service in the military rank given because there are no vacant positions. Privileges such as the granting of a standing military rank, the provision of 5, 10, 15 days of annual leave for the next vacation of military personnel according to the calendar of years of service were created.

Strong social protection, in turn, creates the ground for our officers and soldiers to serve with dedication, devotion to duty, and to improve their professional training. As a result of the complex measures - measures taken, the approach of the defenders of the Motherland to military service has fundamentally changed, responsibility and discipline in the military units have been strengthened, and the feeling of pride and pride in the Motherland has increased in the hearts of all military personnel. In particular, the Regulation on examination and selection for the title of master of the profession in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Appendix 1 to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4905 of 01.12.2020).

Of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on 03.07.2019 PQ-4382-No. "Approval of the regulation on the procedure for assigning and paying one-time benefits to servicemen (employees) who were injured while performing their duties in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan or to the family members of deceased (deceased) servicemen (employees) about" Decision.

Regulation on the organization and implementation of medical examinations in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan during peace and war (registered by the Ministry of Defense No. , approved by the decision No. 8 of the National Guard, No. 5 of the Ministry of Emergency Situations, No. 6 of the State Security Service, No. 23 of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, No. 37 of the Ministry of Health).

11.08.2017 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Resolution No. 619 "On the approval of the regulation on the procedure for granting long-term preferential mortgage loans to military personnel of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the purchase (construction) of residences and individual land plots for building houses."

Regulation on the procedure for granting long-term preferential mortgage loans to military personnel of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the purchase (construction) of residences and individual plots of land for the construction of housing (appendix 1 to the decision of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 619 of 11.08.2017) are among the moral factors of social protection.

As stated by the President, Supreme Commander of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "Strengthening the security and defense potential of our country, conducting an open, pragmatic and active foreign policy" is an important direction.

The essence of the large-scale reforms implemented under the leadership of the President, the Supreme Commander of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev, calls people to understand and feel the human factor in life and their internal capabilities more deeply, and not to shy away from work. The spiritual and physical development of citizens, especially the youth of the country, is combined with the sense of high civic responsibility through the development of the country, the peace of the country and the well-being of the people, as well as the feeling of commitment to the society. will be a solid foundation for its implementation.

Not only military, but also social-political, spiritual-educational and trade-economic issues are gaining importance in the context of the wide-scale reforms implemented in the new Uzbekistan society. That's why President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, relying on the principle of peace, stability and humanity in the increasing position of Uzbekistan in the world community, put the life, dreams, pains and dreams of every person living in our country in the center of our attention and increasing the effectiveness of tasks in this regard as the most important issue on the agenda. Is putting

Today's world is experiencing information attacks. For this reason, analytical assimilation of information is becoming one of the most urgent issues in the thinking of not only the population but also military personnel. Therefore, in accordance with the decrees and decisions of the President, Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the instructions of the Minister of Defense, Lieutenant General Bahadir Kurbanov, and the instructions of the head of the Academy, Colonel Bobur Shayakubov, the interest, mood, and social status of all personnel and social groups cadet studying at our Academy based on the need to study and acquire the skills of analyzing the influence of the destructive ideas of extremists active in the media world with scientific observation, that is, to strengthen the spirit of patriotism and to listeners, sergeants who are taking qualification classes, professors regularly teach "Moral and educational foundations of the fight against fanaticism and extremism", "Combat and moral-spiritual support", "Military psychology", " In addition to such subjects as "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan", in addition, "Spiritual - educational preparation" classes are conducted from an educational and ideological point of view. The goal is to educate our military, which is the pillar of peace and stability in today's global world, in the spirit of strong will and moral-educational trust in all aspects, as our President, Supreme Commander of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev said, "Education in the spirit of loyalty to duty and military patriotism."

Ensuring security, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance in our country was considered the priority of our state policy. Representatives of more than 130 nationalities and peoples living in our country have united in 138 national and cultural centers and live peacefully as children of a big family under the slogan "Uzbekistan is our common home". At the root of this is a great humanitarian policy. In accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2017, the committee "International relations and friendly relations with foreign countries" was established. The main goal of this is to consistently continue the state policy aimed at ensuring inter-ethnic harmony and tolerance in our society.

We must always be alert and vigilant in the present time, when the process of globalization has intensified in the world, competition and mutual contradictions are intensifying on a global scale, threats such as radicalism, terrorism, extremism, proselytism and "mass culture" are expanding.

After all, as stated by the President, Supreme Commander of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "Nowadays in the world, opposition and conflicts between different forces are increasing, fierce struggle for resources is going on. There are new threats to peace and security in our region" [3, p.371].

Life itself requires us to further increase our mobilization through the ideas of "Protect your own home", "Protect your own child". We need to educate our young men and women in the spirit of patriotism, ensuring the inviolability of the country's borders and strengthening the combat potential of our Armed Forces.

Currently, our Armed Forces have improved significantly in terms of organization and structure. The mobility of structures, fighting ability, physical and moral training of the military have increased. Units and units are equipped with modern weapons and combat equipment. Today, in a situation where many countries of the world are facing serious problems of various forms, during the past thirty-two years of independence in our country, especially in the conditions of New Uzbekistan, as a result of the reforms consistently implemented by our respected President in all fields, the life of our people is improving day by day. is catching up with the times. In this

regard, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said in his speech at the 78th session of the UN General Assembly on September 19, 2023: "Development of human capital and education of a creative young generation is one of the strategic tasks that Uzbekistan has set before itself. We consider open and high-quality education for everyone to be the most effective factor for eradicating poverty, improving people's well-being and achieving sustainable economic growth" [4, p.1-2.], he noted. The essence of this is to invite a person to a deeper understanding of his human factor in life and his inner potential. Based on this, in accordance with the principle of social policy, in addition to the monthly salaries of professors with scientific potential who are engaged in pedagogic activities at the Academy, up to 200% bonus is given.

Therefore, as the President, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev pays close attention to the defense sector as well as all fronts, there will be such problems that they will always remain relevant. Among them there are issues related to the spiritual and moral improvement of a person. In fact, in the concept of increasing the efficiency of moral and educational work in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the moral level and intellectual potential of military personnel, pride in our national army, instilling a sense of responsibility for the protection of state security, pays special attention to the fact that tasks such as forming a conscious attitude and an active life position in relation to the processes of globalization taking place in the world and around us are defined. [5, p. 3-4].

Today, high demands are placed on the moral and ethical qualities of all categories of military personnel, and special attention is paid to strengthening the ideological and physical training of personnel, improving their combat skills, and strengthening discipline. As the intellectual and mental stress of the service increases, the need for further development of the officer's discipline remains on the agenda. After all, discipline is the main strength of the army.

Discipline is primarily a concept related to activity and behavior. Discipline is a set of specific requirements for people's behavior that meet social norms established in society. It reflects, firstly, the specific demands of society on individuals and communities, and secondly, the social assessment of the conformity of human behavior to the interests of society, its legitimacy and internal culture. Discipline is a necessary remedy against various forms and degrees of disorder.

The following types of discipline are distinguished according to the spheres of action: state discipline, labor discipline, military discipline, contract-based discipline, financial discipline, technological discipline. These are:

- State discipline - a type of discipline related to the fulfillment of requirements imposed on civil servants;

- labor discipline - a form of social relations that leads its participants to mandatory obedience to certain established rules during the labor process. It is governed by the norms of labor law;

- discipline based on the contract - compliance of the subjects with the obligations and legal relations specified in the contract;

- financial discipline - compliance of subjects with budget, tax and other financial legal instructions;

- technological discipline - compliance of subjects with technological instructions in the production process;

- military discipline - is explained by the rules of compliance of military personnel with established laws, regulations, and orders.

So, thanks to the large-scale work in the military field, strict discipline, spiritual and educational thinking will rise.

"At the moment, we all see how fierce the competition is on the world scale. We can adequately respond to this fierce competition only by widely introducing the achievements of modern science, high technologies and innovation" [6, p.237].

The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 29, 2023 "On measures to increase the effectiveness of education of young people in the military-patriotic spirit" was adopted.

Based on this decision, a 7-chapter concept on educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism was adopted in 2023-2027, and implementation of the decision and concept was determined in 14 territorial units. It is intended to unite young people based on the conceptual idea "The Motherland is great, duty is sacred".

The strength of our army depends on the unity and solidarity of the military personnel and our entire society. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said that as long as this source of spiritual power exists, no evil force can interfere with the independence of Uzbekistan, our peaceful and peaceful life, or turn us back from the path of democratic changes.

As a result of fundamental reforms carried out in recent years, our national army has become a powerful, quick and effective force capable of striking any danger.

Our Armed Forces have established close partnerships with their counterparts in Central Asian countries, and a number of joint training exercises have been held. Visits of high-level military delegations were organized, experience was exchanged in operational and combat training. Such cooperation is becoming an important factor in ensuring regional security and stability, peace and tranquility in our common home called Central Asia.

The system of continuous military education organized on the basis of world standards is developing consistently. Currently, the newly created Military Institute of Information - Communication Technologies and Communication has its proper place.

The Faculty of Military Security and State Defense was established at the Academy of Armed Forces, which prepares officers who will serve in the operational and strategic link of management.

Today, our military personnel are proving in practice that they are not inferior to the military personnel of the armies of the world's leading countries in terms of their level of professional training. At international military training competitions, inter-army and sports competitions, representatives of Uzbekistan demonstrate their skills, mental strength, will to victory, and clearly show that they are the worthy successors of our great ancestors.

Tasks for the further development of the defense-industrial complex capable of supplying our national army with weapons and other necessary means are being solved step by step.

A clear example of this is the modernization and technical re-equipment of the Chirchik aviation repair plant and the enterprise that produces combat ammunition - drugs, and the reorganized scientific and technical potential in them is becoming the basis for the formation of scientific and production clusters in these industries.

In the near future, the ongoing work on the formation of a full-fledged defense sector of our country will not only provide the national army with weapons and equipment, but also create additional jobs, as well as diversify the country's economy.

Military settlements have acquired a modern appearance, outsourcing system has been introduced in the field of material supply services. Over the past years, more than 300 multi-storey houses have been built to provide comfortable and cozy apartments for the families of more than 15 thousand military personnel, about 1000 new jobs have been created for women of military personnel, and 2 thousand 400 military pensioners have been employed.

Our army actively engaged in educating the growing young generation in the spirit of patriotism and love for the motherland, respect for our national values and traditions, and deep knowledge of our glorious history. Organizations such as "Vatanparvar" and "Veterans", as well as the Public Council under the Ministry of Defense, continue to work together to strengthen the education of young people in the military-patriotic spirit and to form an active civil position in them.

In conclusion, the sense of patriotism is strengthened by understanding, feeling and understanding the military sphere. For example, based on the above legal, social, spiritual-educational and political factors, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 23, 2022 "On measures - measures to fundamentally improve the activities of the Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan" "and the implementation of the decisions of September 8, 2022 "On additional measures to increase the moral and spiritual training and fighting spirit of military personnel" is an important strategic factor for the country's development. serves.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (F-79) dated December 14, 2023 "On the preparation and implementation of measures to celebrate the 32nd anniversary of the establishment of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Day of Defenders of the Fatherland" (F-79) and the army - one flesh and one soul!" in order to convey the principle to the general public, it was decided to organize spiritual, educational and cultural promotion events in all regions of our Republic. Based on this, family members of servicemen and employees who died in the defense of the Motherland and national peace, servicemen who became disabled while performing their duty, participants of the Second World War who need attention and support and veterans, as well as charity events related to providing material and moral support to Armed Forces veterans are canceled.

There are certain achievements in the activities of the military-administrative sectors, which have become a reliable bridge between the people and the army. Since the establishment of these sectors, large-scale work has been carried out to modernize military infrastructures and solve accumulated social problems under the motto "The people and the army are one and the same soul" [7, p. 48.].

2024 is the "year of supporting business and youth in Uzbekistan" based on the programmatic idea "From national revival to national rise", educating young people in the spirit of loyalty to the motherland, forming initiative, self-sacrifice, moral qualities and patriotism in them. is one of the important tasks. So, today, under the leadership of the President, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the professional army has become the mainstay of our nation based on the principle of "People and army - one body and one

soul". As a result, our country is strengthening its position in the world axis, as a result of the large-scale reforms being carried out in the new Uzbekistan.

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